

Japanese cultivar cytoplasm affects seedling vigor and heterosis

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In higher plants, cytoplasmic genome variation has been associated with male sterility, miniature kernel mutation, chloroplast deficiency, and disease susceptibility and, in rice, with heterosis and combining ability performance for yield and other traits (Young and Virmani 1990). To date, similar studies in relation to early plant growth are scanty. Thus, we report on the phenotypic effect of japonica rice cytoplasm on seedling vigor and heterosis.

Full diallel crosses were developed from IR50 and three japonica cultivars, namely, Akihikari (AK), Koshihikari (KO), and Todorokiwase (TO). Pre- and postgermination characters related to seedling growth and vigor were observed

on a total of 20 materials per treatment divided into two replications of a completely randomized experiment. After 3 d of incubation at 30 °C, seedlings were placed into sectioned wooden frames with a nylon screen bottom support (1 plot was 5 × 5 cm) and grown in standard culture solution (Kasugai 1959) under glasshouse conditions to minimize environmental effects. Seedlings reared for 16 d and 23 d after sowing (DAS) were then evaluated for different traits. Cytoplasmic effect was assessed using linear correlation and the least significant difference (LSD) test (Gomez and Gomez 1984).

To verify the cytoplasmic effect on seedling phenotypes, correlation analysis using data on overall midparent heterosis

(H_{mp}) (de Leon et al 1999) was performed. The figure shows a substantial decline in linear association between the reciprocals of AK and KO, and between those of AK and TO. This result confirmed the cytoplasmic effect on seedling vigor traits and on the level of H_{mp} attained by certain reciprocal pairs. A detailed analysis of this cytoplasmic effect was performed using the LSD test. Results showed that negatively significant effects were associated with F_1 hybrid seedlings with the Japanese cv. Akihikari as the female parent (see table). The consistently poorer performance of these F_1 hybrids, that is, the negative performance persists regardless of the pollen parent used with AK, suggested cytoplasmic effects with

Cytoplasmic effect on seedling vigor traits in rice.^a

Trait ^b	Cross						LSD (0.05)	LSD (0.01)
	AK/TO– TO/AK	TO/KO KO/TO	TO/IR50– IR50/TO	AK/KO– KO/AK	AK/IR50– IR50/AK	KO/IR50– IR50/KO		
Initial stage								
SW	-0.1501**	0.0263**	0.0152**	0.0114**	-0.0027 na	0.0519**	0.0105	0.0145
GI	-0.8255**	1.5230**	-1.5110**	-1.1530*	-0.8000**	-0.0675 ns	0.5368	0.7396
SL	-0.2975*	0.3917**	-0.0069 ns	-0.0134**	-0.1066 ns	0.0153 ns	0.2713	0.3737
RL	-0.6990 ns	0.9115*	0.0190 ns	-1.4125 ns	-0.8875*	-0.0035 ns	0.7189	0.9906
2nd LEI	-1.8480**	0.6395**	-0.0715 ns	-1.7090**	-1.0635**	0.0000 ns	0.3419	0.4712
16 DAS								
LN	-0.4125**	0.0125 ns	0.0415 ns	-0.0540 ns	-0.1540 ns	0.2125 ns	0.2786	0.3839
SH	-4.3500**	1.9120 ns	2.8120 ns	-4.5500**	-4.3370**	0.6120 ns	2.9215	4.0250
RTL	-1.7120 ns	1.3500 ns	1.6040 ns	0.6710 ns	*1.8000 ns	-1.1000 ns	2.3838	3.2847
2LA	-0.1510**	0.0015 ns	-0.0480 ns	-0.0035 ns	0.0890*	0.0385 ns	0.0876	0.1208
3LA	-0.6700**	0.2575 ns	-0.1090 ns	-0.5050*	-0.5750**	-0.2080 ns	0.3895	0.5368
4LA	-1.5031**	0.4485 ns	0.2075 ns	-0.6990*	-0.8830**	-0.0435 ns	0.6327	0.8718
FW	-0.1490**	0.0365 ns	0.0640 ns	-0.0690*	-0.0405 ns	0.0275 ns	0.0685	0.0942
SDW	-0.0095**	0.0035 ns	0.0045 ns	-0.0085**	-0.0060*	0.0010 ns	0.0055	0.0076
RDW	-0.0030 ns	0.0020 ns	0.0020 ns	-0.0015 ns	-0.0015 ns	0.0015 ns	0.0030	0.0041
23 DAS								
LN	0.0100 ns	0.2500 ns	0.0900 ns	-0.1850 ns	-0.1170 ns	0.2170 ns	0.4461	0.6147
SH	-8.9850**	1.7910 ns	1.4100 ns	-3.3450**	-4.5500**	0.9380 ns	2.3530	3.2422
RTL	-2.6775*	0.7575 ns	0.5900 ns	0.6550 ns	-2.2675*	0.3490 ns	2.1421	2.9516
2LA	-0.0650 ns	0.0525 ns	0.0310 ns	0.0270 ns	-0.1190 ns	0.0575 ns	0.1396	0.1924
3LA	-0.5535*	0.1525 ns	0.2275 ns	-0.1575 ns	-0.7075**	-0.2125 ns	0.4492	0.6189
4LA	-1.0590**	-0.0490 ns	0.5255 ns	0.1335 ns	-0.7805*	0.0130 ns	0.5934	0.8177
5LA	-2.4075**	0.2160 ns	0.7240 ns	-0.3920 ns	-1.7615**	-0.0065 ns	1.1678	1.6091
FW	-0.3075**	0.0950**	0.0375*	-0.0485**	-0.0915**	0.1035**	0.0345	0.0475
SDW	-0.0245**	0.0106 ns	0.0095 ns	-0.0022 ns	-0.0165**	0.0075 ns	0.0119	0.0164
RDW	-0.0061**	0.0029*	0.0020 ns	0.0002 ns	0.0027*	0.0028*	0.0022	0.0031

^aNegatively significant cytoplasmic effect in bold. * = significant at 0.05% level, ** = significant at 0.01% level. ^bSW = initial seed weight; GI = germination index; SL = shoot length; RL = radicle length; 2nd LEI = second leaf emergence index; LN = leaf number; SH = seedling height; RTL = root length; 2LA, 3LA, 4LA, 5LA = second, third, fourth, fifth leaf areas, respectively; FW = fresh weight; SDW = shoot dry weight; RDW = root dry weight. GI and 2nd LEI based on transformed data (square root).

Cytoplasmic or maternal effects on mid-parent heterosis performance of seedling vigor traits revealed by the correlation between reciprocal crosses.

minimal interaction of the nuclear genome. Slightly similar effects were noted from KO/TO (see table). However, such effects were observed in only a few characters of this cross. In contrast, it can be shown that negatively significant effects of AK as a cytoplasmic parent accounted for about 76% of all such cases observed.

These results led us to consider the possibility of a common maternal ancestor shared by both AK and KO. Terry et al (2000) have elucidated such a possibility by a pedigree analysis of AK, which indicates the following simplified genetic lineage involving only female parents: Aikoku - Ginbozu - Norin 8 - Norin 22 - Hatsunishiki - Sasanishiki - Toyonishiki - AK. This suggests that either Aikoku or Ginbozu is the common ancestral parent of AK and KO. This possibility and its implications for the present findings are under investigation.

References

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The course is unique in that it focuses on the needs of rice scientists, it provides a forum for rice scientists to share their experiences and Internet resources with other rice scientists online, and it establishes a learner-centered knowledge network in the form of an online community centered on rice research.

The topics covered by the course include

- What is the Internet
- What is the World Wide Web and what makes it work
- Key Internet terminology
- How to use the Internet for communication with other scientists
- How to use Web browsers
- How to search for information efficiently and effectively
- What are some of the good sources of information for rice scientists available on the Internet
- How to cite Internet documents
- What training opportunities are available online

Connection to the Internet offers national scientists a low-cost communication medium with other scientists linked to the Internet, gives them access to the ever-growing body of information available on and through interlinked computers throughout the world, and provides access to formal and informal training offered online from virtually anywhere.

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